

From Design to Co-Design: Pre-service Science Teachers' Iterative Lesson Planning with GenAI through a Multiliteracies Lens; insights for educational assessment

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Artificial Intelligence and Innovation in Education: Ethical and Technological Dimensions - AI-Education 2025
Official Conference Proceedings

Abstract- This study examines how generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) can mediate reflective lesson design among pre-service science teachers. Drawing on the Learning by Design framework and the pedagogy of multiliteracies, the research explores how fifteen student teachers engaged in iterative dialogue with GenAI while redesigning science lessons. Each participant first created a lesson plan in class and then re-worked it through a recorded series of prompts and responses using AI tools such as ChatGPT, Copilot, and Magic School. The resulting data corpus, fifteen samples of prompts with design rationale and reflective responses, was analysed qualitatively through content analysis guided by the four knowledge processes: Experiencing, Conceptualizing, Analyzing, Applying. Findings showed that AI-supported lesson re-design fostered epistemic awareness, multimodal thinking, and a re-articulation of pedagogical roles. Participants moved from procedural task planning to design reasoning characterised by reflexivity, ethical sensitivity, and multimodal expansion of scientific meaning. In parallel, the iterative prompting sequences revealed how teachers began to reconsider what counts as meaningful evidence of learning, pointing to the potential of GenAI to shape emerging educational assessment thinking skills. The paper argues that iterative human–AI co-design constitutes a process-based design space in which aspects of planning, monitoring, and evaluative judgement become visible as assessment-relevant forms of reasoning.

Keywords. Science education, Learning by Design, Multiliteracies, Generative AI, TPACK, Teacher education, Prompt engineering, educational assessment.

Introduction

Lesson planning is increasingly understood not as a technical procedure but as a space where teachers negotiate meaning, purpose, and representation. This is not limited to teacher education and science education, but ongoing professional development. Recent studies with in-service teachers show that AI integration into teaching scenarios offers meaningful opportunities for fostering multimodal, inclusive, and critically engaged learning (Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts et al., 2025). This shift toward multimodal, culturally responsive pedagogies (Siry, 2021; Kalantzis & Cope, 2021; Zapata, Kalantzis & Cope, 2023) that comes along with the growing presence of generative AI (GenAI) in teachers' everyday design practices can be intentionally integrated in teacher education programmes. Drafting learning objectives, choosing activities, assessment and resources was once a solitary activity; yet now design decisions are negotiated with tools capable of proposing, critiquing, and recombining pedagogical ideas. Within this landscape, iterative human–AI co-design emerges as a distinct pedagogical space in which pre-service teachers can learn to refine ideas, articulate design rationales, and recognise how their choices connect to evidence of learning when designing lessons to foster multiliteracies, particularly when participants justified acceptance, modification, or rejection of AI-generated suggestions, making traces of evaluative judgement visible within the redesign process.

The present study examines the design choices and reasoning of fifteen pre-service science teachers developed with AI after an initial lesson plan developed in class. The lesson plan was revised through short, recorded interactions with GenAI tools (ChatGPT, Copilot, MagicSchool). Rather than evaluating AI outputs, the study focuses on the student-teacher prompts, the critical moments where teachers articulate constraints, question assumptions, and reshape their pedagogical intentions. Lesson redesign, in this light, becomes a process-based inquiry in which teachers test ideas, revisit choices, ask for alternatives and increasingly adopt a design-oriented stance.

Guided by the Learning by Design (LbD) framework and the pedagogy of multiliteracies (Cope & Kalantzis, 2015), this study investigates the epistemic and pedagogical moves embedded in those prompt sequences with the following questions: *How do pre-service science teachers engage in the Learning by Design knowledge processes (Experiencing, Conceptualising, Analysing, Applying) for lesson redesign with GenAI?*

What kinds of pedagogical and epistemic moves do student teachers make when refining lesson activities, representations, and learning environments with AI support? How does the sequence of human–AI interactions reveal shifts in teacher agency, multimodal design decisions, and responsible AI use during lesson redesign, and in what ways does this process begin to shape pre-service teachers' emerging educational assessment thinking skills?

Theoretical background

Science Learning as Multimodal, Cultural, and Dialogic Practice

Contemporary research frames science learning not as passive reception but as a situated, cultural practice in which learners construct meaning through multiple modes of representation. Siry (2021) demonstrates how scientific ideas take shape through gesture, talk, drawing, material manipulation, and embodied interaction. This aligns

closely with multiliteracies theory (New London Group, 1996; Cope & Kalantzis, 2015), which views learning as engagement with a diversity of modes, languages, and cultural perspectives.

Within this framework, a science lesson does not only present content but it provides a learning environment that orchestrates multimodal encounters with science concepts, phenomena or processes through models, animations, diagrams, digital simulations, and collaborative problem-solving. GenAI enters this landscape as an additional interlocutor: it can propose multimodal pathways, suggest representations teachers may not have considered, or combine modalities in novel ways. At the same time, it requires teachers to sift, judge, and adapt its contributions in ways that remain sensitive to disciplinary norms, learner diversity, and ethical considerations.

Learning by Design as a Framework for Understanding Teacher Prompts

Learning by Design (Cope & Kalantzis, 2015; Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts, Cope & Kalantzis, 2024) offers a coherent frame for examining how teachers construct and refine meaning during lesson redesign. Its four knowledge processes (Experiencing, Conceptualising, Analysing, and Applying) describe iterative forms of engagement that can be observed directly in teachers' prompt sequences:

Experiencing occurs when teachers encounter new ideas or sample representations generated by AI.

Conceptualising appears as they articulate learning goals, define categories, or structure lesson phases.

Analysing emerges when they evaluate the feasibility, appropriateness, or ethical implications of AI suggestions.

Applying surfaces when teachers embed refined ideas into concrete lesson activities, adapting them for time, equipment, or classroom dynamics.

Although originally developed to describe student learning, these processes can now map naturally onto teachers' design reasoning. In practice, student teachers often move through these processes implicitly and non-linearly by testing an idea, revising constraints, discarding an unworkable activity, or re-specifying pedagogical intentions. The LbD framework thus provides a useful lens for interpreting their epistemic moves within GenAI-mediated redesign.

Teacher Agency, AI Literacy, and Responsible Mediation

AI in education and its pedagogical value depends less on the tool itself and more on teachers' capacity to evaluate, adapt, and responsibly integrate AI outputs (Smith et al, 2025). Feldman-Maggor, Blonder and Alexandron (2025) propose an AI-extended TPACK model in which teachers require not only technological and pedagogical proficiency but also AI literacy: the ability to interrogate outputs for accuracy, hallucination, bias, relevance, or ethical appropriateness. Also, Blonder & Feldman-Maggor (2024) and Blonder, Feldman-Maggor & Rap (2024) further argue that teacher expertise increasingly lies in interpretive mediation, the capacity to refine or reject AI-generated material rather than accept it. This way, student-teacher choices can signal an emerging sense of responsible design agency by engaging AI as a generative resource while maintaining pedagogical, ethical, and disciplinary integrity.

Process-Based Inquiry and Reflexive Lesson Design

Shifting from static lesson planning to iterative, AI-mediated redesign mirrors broader methodological developments that conceptualize learning, and teaching, as process rather than product (Collier, 2011; Beach & Pedersen, 2013; Smith et al, 2025). From this perspective, the prompts and design reflections function as developmental trajectories and traces of reflective inquiry: they show how teachers negotiate constraints, revisit decisions, and deepen their pedagogical reasoning over time. When teachers move from broad requests to far more precise, context-sensitive prompts, from digital saturation to a balanced multimodal design, and from passive acceptance of AI suggestions to confident critique and selective uptake, their iterations show how prompting with AI can function as a promising ground for reflexivity through design reasoning, encouraging teachers to ask sharper questions, test alternatives, and articulate pedagogical intentions with greater clarity.

Embedding GenAI as a co-designer in Teacher Education and Science Education

The integration of GenAI into lesson design as a co-designer also resonates with emerging scholarship on AI as a core digital literacy, skill or capability. Within the context of biosciences and chemistry education, Smith et al. (2025) argue that GenAI requires more than technical competence: it demands a pedagogical orientation that is reflective, ethically aware, and grounded in disciplinary thinking. They emphasise three interrelated capacities:

Critical discernment – evaluating AI suggestions against curricular aims, scientific accuracy, and contextual appropriateness.

Pedagogical adaptation – reworking AI-generated ideas so they support active, inclusive, and multimodal learning environments.

Epistemic awareness – recognising how AI transforms knowledge practices, reshapes representation, and expands the repertoire of what can count as evidence or explanation. Their work signifies that GenAI should be embedded not as a shortcut but as a participatory design tool that extends and provides evidence for teacher thinking while requiring human judgment at every stage. This insight aligns directly with the design trajectories observed in the present study, where student teachers treated AI as a stimulus for exploration rather than a source of authoritative answers. In the same vein, AI literacy entails effective use of GenAI aligning with reflective engagement when teachers evaluate suggestions, negotiate constraints, and redirect prompts to align with multiliteracies principles and real classroom conditions.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative, process-based content-analysis design to investigate how pre-service science teachers engaged with generative AI during iterative lesson redesign (Collier, 2011; Beach & Pedersen, 2013).

Fifteen pre-service science teachers, enrolled in a university course on Teaching Multiliteracies and Learning by Design for Science Education, created an initial lesson plan individually in class and subsequently revised it through a short, guided interaction with one or more GenAI tools (ChatGPT, Copilot, MagicSchool). Each participant submitted:

- a) the original lesson plan,
- b) screenshots of all prompts they wrote during the redesign, and justifications (of modifications or why they kept or rejected suggestions)
- c) the revised lesson artefact.

The analytical dataset comprise fifteen prompt chains (one per participant) and does not compare initial and final lesson plans. However, the dataset included in this study included lesson plans that were assessed by the instructor as pedagogically coherent, appropriate for the intended age group, and aligned with the overarching multiliteracies and Learning by Design framework, ensuring that all participants entered the initial and redesign phase with a baseline level of instructional quality.

Although the focus is on tracing how learners organise, revise, or justify ideas over time (Beach & Pedersen, 2019), in this study, the “process” was not reconstructed as a turn-by-turn chronological map. Instead, the unit of analysis was the prompt itself as an epistemic move within the wider redesign activity. Each prompt and its reasoning (i.e. design reflections during real-time design conversations through screenshots) was examined for what it revealed about the teacher’s reasoning, decision-making, or representational intentions at that moment. This allowed us to identify recurring patterns, such as how student-teachers shifted from broad requests (“make the lesson more interactive”) to more principled design considerations (e.g., age-appropriateness, multimodal fit, adjustment of activity timing, or critical rejection of unsuitable AI suggestions).

A directed content-analysis approach (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005) was employed, using the Learning by Design knowledge processes, i.e. Experiencing, Conceptualizing, Analyzing, and Applying (Cope & Kalantzis, 2015; Cope, Kalantzis, & Sears Smith, 2021), as flexible lenses against which epistemic choices could be interpreted. Parallel to this frame, epistemic awareness, design reasoning, reflexive positioning, ethical sensitivity, multiliteracies-oriented shifts in representation, pedagogical role re-articulation, and human–AI interaction patterns illuminated how the research questions were addressed.

Findings

The analysis of student-teacher prompts revealed a pattern of reasoning that was not uniform across participants. Instead, the prompts showed varied but recognisable tendencies in how pre-service teachers used GenAI to negotiate lesson redesign within the Learning by Design (LbD) framework, while signifying epistemic stance, design reasoning, and pedagogical agency. Table 1 summarises the codes emerging from the dataset.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Simplified code label</i>	<i>Participants (n)</i>	<i>Participants (%)</i>
<i>AI ethics & responsibility</i>	<i>Bias awareness</i>	3	20.0
	<i>Checking / validating AI outputs</i>	5	33.3
	<i>Equity & access concerns</i>	4	26.7

	<i>Ethical limits</i>	1	6.7
	<i>Ethical reflection</i>	8	53.3
<i>Design reasoning & stance</i>	<i>Awareness of learning / knowledge aims</i>	12	80.0
	<i>Explaining and justifying changes</i>	13	86.7
	<i>Reflective self-positioning</i>	12	80.0
	<i>Sensitivity to values / implications</i>	7	46.7
<i>Working with AI</i>	<i>Agreement with AI ideas</i>	8	53.3
	<i>Building on AI suggestions</i>	9	60.0
	<i>Mismatch with classroom reality</i>	4	26.7
	<i>Critical adaptation</i>	9	60.0
	<i>Critical rejection</i>	10	66.7
<i>Learning by Design processes</i>	<i>Experiencing – exploring options</i>	7	46.7
	<i>Conceptualising-organising lesson ideas</i>	13	86.7
	<i>Analysing – checking feasibility</i>	13	86.7
	<i>Applying – integrating into plans</i>	10	66.7
<i>Multimodal design</i>	<i>Expanding representations</i>	10	66.7
	<i>Purposeful use of modes</i>	9	60.0
	<i>Critiquing representations</i>	6	40.0
<i>Teacher roles & agency</i>	<i>Shift toward facilitator / designer</i>	7	46.7
	<i>Teacher as co-designer with AI</i>	15	100.0
	<i>Teacher agency & critical stance</i>	11	73.3

Table 1. Emerging codes when embedding GenAI as a co-designer in Teacher Education and Science Education

RQ1. How do pre-service science teachers engage in the Learning by Design knowledge processes (Experiencing, Conceptualising, Analysing, Applying) when redesigning lessons with GenAI?

Across the dataset, all four LbD knowledge processes appeared, though with different levels of prominence. Conceptualising accounted for the largest share of coded material, followed by Analysing, Experiencing, and Applying (Table 1).

Experiencing

Participants frequently began their interaction by requesting examples, alternative representations, or ways to “make the lesson more interesting.” These early prompts often reflected uncertainty and exploratory engagement rather than firm pedagogical commitments. Teachers treated the AI’s suggestions as a space to “see what is possible,” especially regarding multimodal representations, use of digital tools, or ways to motivate students. Here is an example.

P2: (Prompt) Create an interactive lesson plan for the unit “The Cell: The Unit of Life” for Grade 7 Biology, to be completed within 45 minutes.

Experiencing was therefore visible in prompts that probed possibilities without yet making design decisions.

Conceptualising

The largest category concerned prompts where teachers articulated goals, re-structured lesson sequences, or attempted to refine the organisation of activities. Many clarified learning objectives, asked for alignment with curriculum expectations, or explored ways to better connect introductory tasks with main activities. Here is an example:

P4: (Prompt) Meet Objectives: For students to understand how the cell functions, what its main parts are, and the role each part plays. Additionally, for them to use images and models to remember these more easily and to collaborate with one another.

Conceptualising also appeared when teachers explicitly asked the AI to “rephrase,” “reorganise,” or “place activities in the six-column format,” revealing deliberate attempts to develop coherent lesson architecture.

*P2: (Prompt) Repeat using a six-column template:
Learning process (B–Experiencing, A–Analysing, D–Explicit instruction, E–Applying)
Literacies, media, and modalities
Student activities
Time
Assessment
Learning outcomes*

Analyzing

These prompts appeared when teachers questioned feasibility (e.g., equipment constraints), age-appropriateness, time allocation, classroom realities, and the pedagogical value of AI-generated suggestions. For example,

P11 : (Prompt) I asked ChatGPT for alternative teaching methods, although I considered the suggestion of “experimental exploration using a microscope” appropriate, because it gives students the opportunity to experience the essence of the lesson rather than simply observe and interact with imaginary means in the digital world or with simulations.

Teachers routinely rejected proposals that were overly time-consuming, technologically demanding, or misaligned with their intended learning outcomes. Several questioned whether overuse of digital tools would distract students and requested analog or tactile alternatives (e.g., microscopes, printed diagrams). This category demonstrates how teachers positioned themselves as evaluators rather than adopters of AI output.

Applying

The Applying process appeared when teachers incorporated selected ideas into concrete plan revisions. Many worksheets replaced long theoretical presentations with short videos, modified group work structures, or added short assessments such as matching tasks or Kahoot quizzes.

P6 Prompt: After the guidance I received [...] I decided that I would implement the idea it initially gave me for the ice-breaker question (“Where would you go on holiday if you were a cell?”).

The presence of Applying in one fifth of all codes illustrates that participants did not simply apply suggested design, but they reflected on it and actively shaped it.

RQ2. What kinds of pedagogical and epistemic moves do student teachers make when refining lesson activities, representations, and learning environments with AI support?

The pedagogical and epistemic moves were captured across several cross-cutting codes. Three themes stood out: design reasoning, multimodal expansion, and criteria-based decision-making (Table 1).

Design reasoning prompts were among the most frequent. These included justifications for modifying activities, identifying gaps in prior designs, rejecting suggestions due to classroom constraints, and proposing refinements. Teachers moved from vague requests (“make the lesson more interactive”) toward targeted specifications (e.g., “include an introductory activity that bridges the previous lesson on organism characteristics”). Many sought a balance between creativity and practical implementation, an emerging pedagogical stance that treats lesson design as an argument or as an exercise in weighing alternatives. For example,

P8 Prompt: In my view, presented in this way the lesson becomes teacher-centred, and students lose interest and become distracted. For this reason, I asked it to make the following modifications: the theoretical presentation should last 10 minutes and should include the cellular organelles and the differences between animal and plant cell organelles. At the same time, during the theoretical presentation, images of the organelles should be displayed via the projector or interactive whiteboard so that students can complete questions 2 and 3 of the worksheet.

Epistemic moves also concerned representational variety. Teachers asked for or refined multimodal elements such as 3D videos, printed diagrams, collaborative posters, interactive simulations, role-play, and analog materials. Here is an example:

P3 Prompt: I like the fourth activity very much and will incorporate it into my lesson plan. I would implement it in class as follows: assuming my class consists of 20 students, I would divide them into five groups of four, and each group would take on the role of an organelle (nucleus, mitochondrion, chloroplast, vacuole, cell membrane). I would ask each group to present the functions of their organelle with the aim of convincing the class that their role in the cell is the most important, and I would give the group members five minutes to discuss what they will say.

Importantly, several prompts resisted digital saturation, asking for tactile alternatives or more varied literacies. This pattern suggests an awareness of multimodal pedagogy not as “add more media” but as deliberate orchestration of modes for meaning-making, in accordance with multiliteracies principles.

A notable proportion of prompts expressed evaluation criteria, especially concerning time allocation, cognitive load, developmental appropriateness, feasibility with available school equipment, classroom management, ethical/cultural considerations and accuracy or clarity of scientific representation. For example,

[P13] Lack of the human element. AI cannot fully perceive the learning needs of a classroom.

This shows teachers exercising judgement, not simply following AI suggestions. Ethical sensitivity occasionally surfaced, for example, when teachers questioned proposed activities that might reinforce misconceptions or fail to support inclusive perspectives.

RQ3. How does the human–AI interaction reveal shifts in teacher agency, multimodal decision-making, and responsible AI use during the redesign process?

Two patterns dominated: a gradual assertion of pedagogical agency and a marked tendency toward responsible mediation of AI outputs (Table 1).

In table 1, critical rejection frequency was slightly higher than critical uptake and significantly higher than alignment with AI suggestions. Teachers’ roles shifted from tentative experimenters to more confident decision-makers as teachers began directing the AI with far more specificity by modifying, narrowing, or rejecting suggestions. More specifically, several participants discarded AI-generated activities because they required equipment unavailable in Greek public schools. Others replaced AI-proposed theoretical lectures with collaborative tasks to maintain student engagement. Many insisted on detailed, step-by-step student actions when AI outputs were overly general. This illustrates an increasing sense of ownership over pedagogical decisions.

Across the dataset, all participants (100%) produced prompts coded under Teacher as Co-Designer. These prompts demonstrated that student teachers engaged in negotiating, adjusting, or reshaping AI-generated suggestions rather than accepting them as provided. This pattern appeared consistently in every prompt and was present in 7.1% of all coded segments.

Responsible use of AI appeared as requests to avoid overwhelming digital modalities or to ensure equity for students without device access, questions about the accuracy of cellular structures in videos or simulations, and decisions to exclude tasks that risked cognitive overload or marginalised quieter students. Such reasoning accounted for approximately 14% of coded segments and reflected a precautionary stance: teachers wanted to harness AI’s generativity while maintaining pedagogical and ethical integrity.

The interaction patterns showed that AI often proposes ambitious ideas of multimodal activities. Teachers evaluated feasibility, time, equipment, and cognitive load and either adapted or replaced the AI output with a more balanced multimodal approach. This

dynamic suggests that novice teachers are negotiating not only lesson content but also what responsible, inclusive representation looks like in a multimodal science classroom.

Discussion

The material generated through the redesign activity offers a grounded view of how student-teachers think while they work on lesson planning alongside GenAI (Beach & Pedersen, 2019). Reading across the prompt sequences, what stands out is not the presence of ready-made solutions, but the steady effort to refine ideas, weigh alternatives, and make decisions that felt workable for real classrooms (Blonder, Feldman-Maggor, & Rap, 2024). Rather than treating AI suggestions as final, most participants handled them as starting points that needed to be questioned, reshaped, or sometimes set aside (Table 1). This stance is consistent with studies that highlight interpretive mediation and teacher responsibility in AI-supported lesson design and requires further research on that (Feldman-Maggor, Blonder, & Alexandron, 2025).

A recurring tendency across the cases was a careful attention to structure and purpose (Cope & Kalantzis, 2015). Many prompts focused on reorganising lesson phases, clarifying what an activity was meant to achieve, or adjusting a task so that it matched the age group and the available time (Kember et al., 2000). In this respect, the interaction with the tool did not simply generate more material; it encouraged participants to slow down and spell out why one design option made more sense than another (Carless & Boud, 2018). Several teachers used their prompts to articulate concerns that experienced colleagues often express informally, for example, when a representation risks confusing learners, or when a proposed activity looks engaging but is likely to be impractical in everyday school conditions (Blonder & Feldman-Maggor, 2024).

Multimodal design played a similar role (Siry, 2021). Participants were open to new ideas for visuals, digital resources, and interactive tasks, yet they approached these with caution (Zapata, Kalantzis, & Cope, 2023). Some chose to limit the number of digital elements suggested by the tool, either because of access issues or because they sensed that too many parallel stimuli might distract from the scientific ideas they wanted learners to grasp (Cope, Kalantzis, & Searsmith, 2021). Their decisions suggest that the move toward multimodality was not about accumulating modes, but about choosing forms of representation that could genuinely support understanding (Katsampoxaki-Hodgetts et al., 2025).

Across the dataset, there was also a noticeable shift in tone as the redesign progressed (Beach & Pedersen, 2019). Early prompts were often exploratory and tentative. Later ones became more specific, with participants directing the tool toward tighter constraints, clearer goals, or alternative options that better aligned with their intentions (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). In several cases, teachers rejected entire proposals because they did not fit their context or because they conflicted with the kind of learning environment they wanted to foster (Zhai, 2023). These moments do not signal opposition to AI; rather, they show teachers negotiating their role as designers and claiming responsibility for the final shape of the lesson.

Taken together, the prompt sequences reveal lesson redesign as an iterative craft practice (Cope & Kalantzis, 2015). Ideas were tried out, revised, and re-worked in light of classroom realities (Beach & Pedersen, 2019). Through this process, participants made aspects of their design reasoning more explicit, particularly when they justified modifications, rejected unsuitable proposals, or specified constraints related to time, resources, or student needs (Nicol, 2020). For teacher educators, these written traces are valuable not because they “measure” competence, but because they offer glimpses into how novice teachers are beginning to articulate the thinking that sits behind their planning choices (Carless & Boud, 2018).

Implications for Assessment and Teacher Education Practice

The activity used in this study suggests a number of practical directions for programmes that wish to integrate GenAI into lesson-design work in meaningful ways (Smith et al., 2025). Rather than presenting AI as a shortcut for generating plans, the redesign process positioned it as a conversational partner that invites teachers to explain, refine, and sometimes defend their decisions (Blonder & Feldman-Maggor, 2024). This orientation may help students move beyond surface-level prompt use toward a more reflective stance on why lessons are designed as they are (Kalantzis & Cope, 2021).

First, the findings point to the value of scaffolding human-AI prompting as a design practice (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). Prompts that simply “ask for ideas” tended to produce generic material, whereas prompts that specified constraints, intentions, and learner characteristics supported richer reasoning (Kember et al., 2000). Teacher-education courses may therefore benefit from modelling prompt sequences that begin broad and gradually become more focused, encouraging student-teachers to articulate their rationale as they iterate (Cope & Kalantzis, 2015).

Second, the work highlights the importance of supporting multimodal judgement rather than multimodal accumulation (Zapata, Kalantzis, & Cope, 2023). Participants were selective in their uptake of digital and visual elements, often reducing or adapting suggestions to fit their context (Siry, 2021). Designing activities that ask students to justify representational choices, not just add resources, may strengthen this kind of professional sensitivity (Cope, Kalantzis, & Sears Smith, 2021).

Third, the redesign process created space for discussion of practical and ethical boundaries: feasibility, workload, access, and the kinds of participation different activities invite (Blonder & Feldman-Maggor, 2024). Embedding opportunities for group reflection around these decisions can help connect individual prompting choices with broader conversations about inclusive, thoughtful classroom practice (Erduran, & Levrini, 2024).

For colleagues involved in designing assessment in teacher-education programmes, the redesign activity used in this study offers an alternative way of thinking about what can be assessed, and how learning can be made discussable without relying solely on finished lesson artefacts (Carless & Boud, 2018). The prompts and accompanying justifications did not replace traditional assignments, but they added another layer: they made it possible to see how student-teachers arrived at their decisions, how they negotiated constraints, and how they revised or rejected options that did not align with their intentions (Nicol, 2020). For assessment developers, this suggests the value of

creating tasks that invite students to share the reasoning behind their design choices, not only the end product (Beach & Pedersen, 2019). Such approaches do not require complex scoring systems; they can be built around brief narrative commentaries, short design memos, or structured moments of reflection that accompany iterative redesign (Carless & Boud, 2018). Where programmes choose to include GenAI as part of lesson-design activities, assessments may therefore focus less on whether a plan looks polished and more on how teachers explain their choices, adapt suggestions to their context, and show awareness of the consequences different design paths might have for learners (Kalantzis & Cope, 2021). In this sense, the redesign process can serve as a useful assessment space for nurturing professional judgement in a formative, developmental way, while still respecting the diversity of pedagogical orientations that student-teachers bring to their work (Cope, Kalantzis, & Sears, 2021).

Conclusion.

Overall, the study suggests that GenAI can be used productively in teacher education when it is positioned as a tool that supports design exploration, negotiation of constraints, and careful reasoning about pedagogical choices, rather than as an automatic lesson generator (Smith et al., 2025). Future iterations of this work could extend these activities into school placements, allowing student-teachers to revisit their redesign decisions in light of how lessons unfold in real classrooms following Design-Based Research protocols (Philippakos, Howell, & Pellegrino, (2021).

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